

Questionnaire

Name: 林伟康

Gender: 男

Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 14; 3. 15

Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 30; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 22, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 26, -, (X);
24, -, (✓); 25, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 25, -, (✓);

23, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
 0.75V: 22, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓);
25, -, (X); 23, +, (✓); 18, -, (✓); 26, +, (✓);
22, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

0.50V: 17, +, (✓); 27, +, (X); 17, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
23, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 26, +, (✓); 26, -, (✓);
25, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓);

0.25V: 23, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 18, -, (X); 27, -, (X);
18, +, (X); 19, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 27, -, (X);
19, +, (X); 17, -, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock:	Vibration frequency <u>11</u>	Voltage <u>27</u>
2 Sandpaper:	Vibration frequency <u>20</u>	Voltage <u>25.5</u>
3 Denim:	Vibration frequency <u>26</u>	Voltage <u>24.5</u>
5 Glass:	Vibration frequency <u>110</u>	Voltage <u>20</u>
4 Silk:	Vibration frequency <u>53</u>	Voltage <u>22</u>

4. Texture discrimination

2, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);
4, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);
3, (✓); 1, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

0, (✓); 0, (✓); 0, (✓); 0, (✓);
1 → (X); 2, (✓); 00 (X); 1, (✓);
0, (✓); 2 → (X); →

1,), >, 0, 0, 0.

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

6 (✓); K (✓); 8 (✓); w (✓);
L (✓); N (✓); 0 (xO); X (✓);
O (✓); Y (✓); K (✓); 3 (✓);
Z (✓); I (xI); V (✓); G (✓);
N (✓); L (✓); T (✓); 0 (✓);

林伟康
Weikang LIN

Questionnaire

Name: 张东胜

Gender: 男

Age: _____

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 14

Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 29; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 24, +, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓);

23, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓);

22, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓);

0.75V: 17, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓);

17, +, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 23, +, (X);

~~15~~ 15, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓);

0.50V: 16, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

24, -, (X); 15, -, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 16, -, (✓);

23, -, (X); 24, +, (X);

0.25V: 24, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 18, -, (✓); 20, -, (X);

16, +, (✓); 16, -, (X); 15, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓);

20, +, (X); 19, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

0 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 7

Voltage 29

1 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 23

Voltage 27

2 Denim: Vibration frequency 28

Voltage 26

4 Glass: Vibration frequency 99

Voltage 23

3 Silk: Vibration frequency 55

Voltage 23.5

4. Texture discrimination

0, (✓); 1, (✓); 1, (✓); 2, (✓);

3, (X); 4, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (✓);

4, (X); 2, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

0, (✓); 0 $\rightarrow$ 0, (X); 0 $\rightarrow$ 0, (X); 1, (✓);

2, (✓); 0, (✓); 0, (✓); 1 $\rightarrow$ 1, (X);

1, (✓); 0, (✓);

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

I (✓); I (✓); J (✓); P (✓);
M (x→N); F (✓); V (✓); G (✓);
X (✓); 5 (✓); N (✓); 8 (x→3);
Y (✓); H (✓); 4 (✓); L (✓);
Z (x→2); A (✓); 9 (✓); B (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 李雪松

Gender: 男

Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 11; 2. 12; 3. 12

Maximum toleration: 1. 26; 2. 27; 3. 26

2. Intensity discriminatio

13-23

1V: 21, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 21, +, (✓);

17, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓);

18, +, (✓); 13, +, (✓);

0.75V: 16, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

18, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 13, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓);

22, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓);

0.50V: 21, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 13, +, (✓);

16, +, (✓); 13, +, (✓); 22, +, (X); 13, -, (✓);

21, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓);

0.25V: 20, +, (✓); 22, -, (X); 19, +, (✓); 13, -, (✓);

22, +, (X); 14, -, (✓); 13, +, (✓); 19, -, (X);

15, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 12

Voltage 26

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 20

Voltage 25.5

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 33

Voltage 24

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 113

Voltage 20

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 46

Voltage 22

4. Texture discrimination

4, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓); 3, (✓);

2, (✓); 2, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓);

1, (✓); 4, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

1, (✓); 2, (✓); 6, (✓); 6, (✓);

2, (✓); 1, (✓); 2, (X→); 6, (✓);

6, (✓); 3, (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 213 ID Gender: 男 Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 11; 2. 12; 3. 13
 Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 29; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

14-24

1V: 19, -, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
18, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓);
 0.75V: 19, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 20, -, (X);
17, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
 0.50V: 19, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 19, -, (X); 14, -, (✓);
23, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓);
 0.25V: 15, -, (X); 15, -, (X); 15, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓);
22, -, (✓); 19, -, (X); 14, +, (X); 22, -, (✓);
14, -, (X); 21, -, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock:	Vibration frequency <u>10</u>	Voltage <u>27.5</u>
2 Sandpaper:	Vibration frequency <u>18</u>	Voltage <u>27</u>
3 Denim:	Vibration frequency <u>31</u>	Voltage <u>26</u>
5 Glass:	Vibration frequency <u>107</u>	Voltage <u>25</u>
4 Silk:	Vibration frequency <u>54</u>	Voltage <u>23</u>

4. Texture discrimination

1, (✓); 4, (✓); 4, (✓); 1, (✓);
2, (✓); 4, (✓); 3, (✓); 3, (✓);
2, (✓); 2, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

3, (✓); 5, (✓); 6, (X→4); 1, (✓);
2, (✓); 1, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (X→1);
6, (✓); 6, (✓);

1 2 3 4 5 6
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4

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

J (✓); W (✓); E (✓); H (✓);
O (X→0); K (✓); B (X→3); R (✓);
U (✓); X (✓); G (✓); C (✓);
Q (✓); F (✓); I (✓); L (✓);
2 (X→0); V (✓); P (✓); 3 (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 刘敏新

Gender: 男

Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 14; 2. 14; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 25; 2. 26; 3. 25

2. Intensity discriminatio

15-23

1V: 18, -, (✓); 17, -, (X); 21, -, (X); 22, -, (X);

18, +, (✓); 19, -, (X); 19, +, (X); 17, +, (X);

18, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓);

0.75V: 22, +, (✓); 20, -, (X); 15, -, (X); 16, ~~19~~ +, (X);

19, +, (✓); 15, +, (X); 16, +, (X); 21, -, (X);

17, -, (X); 22, -, (X);

0.50V: 16, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 21, +, (X);

17, -, (X); 16, -, (X); 21, +, (X); 20, -, (X);

18, -, (✓); 17, -, (X);

0.25V: 17, +, (✓); 17, +, (X); 19, -, (X); 17, +, (X);

21, +, (X); 20, -, (X); 18, +, (X); 16, -, (X);

18, +, (X); 19, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 9

Voltage 23

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 18

Voltage 22.5

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 33

Voltage 22

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 113

Voltage 21

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 57

Voltage 21.5

4. Texture discrimination

3, (✓); 5, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);

2, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓); 3, (✓);

5, (✓); 5, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

3, (✓); 6, (✓); 1, (✓); 2, (✓);

1, (✓); 1, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓);

6, (✓); 5, (✓);

1 2 3 4 5 6
|) > ○ ○ ○

Questionnaire

Name: FF

Gender: 男

Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 14; 3. 14

Maximum toleration: 1. 29; 2. 29; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 18, -, (U); 23, +, (U); 19, -, (U); 19, -, (U);
23, -, (U); 18, -, (U); 22, -, (U); 22, -, (U);
24, +, (U); 22, -, (U);

0.75V: 18, -, (U); 21, +, (U); 19, -, (U); 19, +, (U);
20, -, (U); 24, +, (U); 15, -, (U); 23, +, (U);
21, -, (U); 18, +, (U);

0.50V: 24, +, (U); 16, +, (U); 15, -, (U); 19, +, (U);
21, -, (U); 19, -, (U); 23, -, (U); 20, -, (U);
20, +, (U); 15, -, (U);

0.25V: 15, -, (X); 17, -, (U); 15, +, (U); 24, -, (U);
21, +, (U); 15, +, (X); 22, +, (U); 18, -, (X);
23, +, (U); 19, +, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock:	Vibration frequency <u>9</u>	Voltage <u>28</u>
2 Sandpaper:	Vibration frequency <u>12</u>	Voltage <u>27.5</u>
3 Denim:	Vibration frequency <u>27</u>	Voltage <u>27</u>
5 Glass:	Vibration frequency <u>50</u> 110	Voltage <u>24</u> 24
4 Silk:	Vibration frequency <u>50</u> 100	Voltage <u>26</u> 24

4. Texture discrimination

1, (U); 4, (U); 3, (U); 5, (U);
4, (U); 1, (U); 1, (U); 1, (U);
2, (U); 5, (U);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

3, (U); 5, (X → 4); 4, (U); 4, (U);
5, (U); 2, (U); 6, (U); 3, (U);
3, (U); 1, (U);

1 2 3 4 5 6
 1 1 1 0 0 0

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

S (x→8); N (✓); M (✓); 3 (✓);
G (✓); A (✓); R (✓); O (✓);
2 (✓); L (✓); K (✓); I (✓);
Y (✓); C (✓); T (✓); 6 (x→0);
0 (x→0); 4 (✓); V (✓); U (✓);

7k

(faint handwritten notes and calculations, including numbers like 12, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 100)

(faint handwritten notes and calculations, including numbers like 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 100)

(faint handwritten notes and calculations, including numbers like 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 100)

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(faint handwritten notes and calculations, including numbers like 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 100)

Questionnaire

Name: 谢浩然

Gender: 男

Age: 26

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 14

Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 29; 3. 29

15-25

2. Intensity discriminatio

1V: 15, +, (✓); 18, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓);

19, +, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓);

15, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓);

0.75V: 19, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

22, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓);

22, +, (✓); 17, +, (X);

0.50V: 18, -, (X); 15, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓);

20, +, (✓); 18, -, (X); 17, +, (X); 19, +, (✓);

23, -, (✓); 21, +, (✓);

0.25V: 22, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 21, +, (X); 20, +, (✓);

22, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 20, +, (X); 20, +, (✓);

22, +, (X); 24, +, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 7

Voltage 27

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 20

Voltage 26

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 35

Voltage 25.5

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 56 & 112

Voltage 24

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 112 & 56

Voltage 25

4. Texture discrimination

1, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (X→1); 1, (✓);

4, (✓); 5, (✓); 4, (✓); 3, (✓);

2, (✓); 1, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

6, (✓); 3, (✓); 5, (✓); 1, (✓);

5, (✓); 5, (✓); 5, (✓); 4, (✓);

6, (✓); 5, (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 张鹏

Gender: 男

Age: _____

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 28; 3. 29

16 → 26

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 21, -, (✓); 21, +, (X); 20, +, (X); 17, -, (X);

18, -, (X); 22, +, (X); 17, -, (X); 19, +, (X);

17, -, (X); 24, +, (X);

0.75V: 19, +, (X); 24, +, (X); 23, -, (X); 25, -, (X);

20, +, (X); 25, +, (X); 20, +, (X); 21, +, (X);

21, -, (X); 17, +, (X);

0.50V: 17, +, (X); 20, +, (X); 25, -, (X); 16, +, (X);

19, +, (X); 22, -, (X); 18, -, (X); 18, +, (X);

26, +, (X); 23, -, (X);

0.25V: 24, +, (X); 20, +, (X); 24, +, (X); 19, -, (X);

17, -, (X); 25, +, (X); 16, -, (X); 22, +, (X);

22, +, (X); 17, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 7

Voltage 27

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 23

Voltage 26

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 35

Voltage 25.5

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 120

Voltage 23

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 48

Voltage 25

4. Texture discrimination

1, (✓); 3, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓);

4, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓); 5, (✓);

5, (✓); 2, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

1, (X→2); 4, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓);

6, (✓); 2, (✓); 3, (✓); 1, (✓);

2, (✓); 4, (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 余金科 Gender: 男 Age: 23

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 12; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 28

2. Intensity discriminatio

15-25

1V: 18, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 21, +, (✓);
16, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
24, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);

0.75V: 16, -, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 15, -, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓);

0.50V: 24, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
19, +, (✓); 15, -, (X); 21, +, (X); 20, -, (✓);
24, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);

0.25V: 24, -, (X); 23, -, (X); 16, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 19, +, (X);
21, +, (X); 23, +, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock:	Vibration frequency <u>7</u>	Voltage <u>28</u>
2 Sandpaper:	Vibration frequency <u>18</u>	Voltage <u>27</u>
3 Denim:	Vibration frequency <u>35</u>	Voltage <u>26.5</u>
5 Glass:	Vibration frequency <u>98</u>	Voltage <u>25</u>
4 Silk:	Vibration frequency <u>56</u>	Voltage <u>26</u>

4. Texture discrimination

4, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓); 3, (✓);
3, (✓); 5, (✓); 4, (✓); 1, (✓);
3, (✓); 2, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

1, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓); 5, (✓);
2, (X→1); 5, (✓); 2, (✓); 6, (✓);
4, (✓); 3, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
 1 2 3 4 5 6

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

Z (✓); H (✓); X (✓); V (x, 0);
G (x, 6); V (✓); L (✓); D (✓);
B (✓); W (✓); O (✓); 5 (✓);
P (✓); 6 (x, 0); Y (✓); C (✓);
I (✓); 4 (✓); M (✓); 8 (✓);

余全科

20-21

1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10. 11. 12. 13. 14. 15. 16. 17. 18. 19. 20. 21. 22. 23. 24. 25. 26. 27. 28. 29. 30. 31. 32. 33. 34. 35. 36. 37. 38. 39. 40. 41. 42. 43. 44. 45. 46. 47. 48. 49. 50. 51. 52. 53. 54. 55. 56. 57. 58. 59. 60. 61. 62. 63. 64. 65. 66. 67. 68. 69. 70. 71. 72. 73. 74. 75. 76. 77. 78. 79. 80. 81. 82. 83. 84. 85. 86. 87. 88. 89. 90. 91. 92. 93. 94. 95. 96. 97. 98. 99. 100.

1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10. 11. 12. 13. 14. 15. 16. 17. 18. 19. 20. 21. 22. 23. 24. 25. 26. 27. 28. 29. 30. 31. 32. 33. 34. 35. 36. 37. 38. 39. 40. 41. 42. 43. 44. 45. 46. 47. 48. 49. 50. 51. 52. 53. 54. 55. 56. 57. 58. 59. 60. 61. 62. 63. 64. 65. 66. 67. 68. 69. 70. 71. 72. 73. 74. 75. 76. 77. 78. 79. 80. 81. 82. 83. 84. 85. 86. 87. 88. 89. 90. 91. 92. 93. 94. 95. 96. 97. 98. 99. 100.

1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10. 11. 12. 13. 14. 15. 16. 17. 18. 19. 20. 21. 22. 23. 24. 25. 26. 27. 28. 29. 30. 31. 32. 33. 34. 35. 36. 37. 38. 39. 40. 41. 42. 43. 44. 45. 46. 47. 48. 49. 50. 51. 52. 53. 54. 55. 56. 57. 58. 59. 60. 61. 62. 63. 64. 65. 66. 67. 68. 69. 70. 71. 72. 73. 74. 75. 76. 77. 78. 79. 80. 81. 82. 83. 84. 85. 86. 87. 88. 89. 90. 91. 92. 93. 94. 95. 96. 97. 98. 99. 100.

1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10. 11. 12. 13. 14. 15. 16. 17. 18. 19. 20. 21. 22. 23. 24. 25. 26. 27. 28. 29. 30. 31. 32. 33. 34. 35. 36. 37. 38. 39. 40. 41. 42. 43. 44. 45. 46. 47. 48. 49. 50. 51. 52. 53. 54. 55. 56. 57. 58. 59. 60. 61. 62. 63. 64. 65. 66. 67. 68. 69. 70. 71. 72. 73. 74. 75. 76. 77. 78. 79. 80. 81. 82. 83. 84. 85. 86. 87. 88. 89. 90. 91. 92. 93. 94. 95. 96. 97. 98. 99. 100.

1. 2. 3. 4. 5. 6. 7. 8. 9. 10. 11. 12. 13. 14. 15. 16. 17. 18. 19. 20. 21. 22. 23. 24. 25. 26. 27. 28. 29. 30. 31. 32. 33. 34. 35. 36. 37. 38. 39. 40. 41. 42. 43. 44. 45. 46. 47. 48. 49. 50. 51. 52. 53. 54. 55. 56. 57. 58. 59. 60. 61. 62. 63. 64. 65. 66. 67. 68. 69. 70. 71. 72. 73. 74. 75. 76. 77. 78. 79. 80. 81. 82. 83. 84. 85. 86. 87. 88. 89. 90. 91. 92. 93. 94. 95. 96. 97. 98. 99. 100.

Questionnaire

Name: 王源伟

Gender: 男

Age: 23

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 11; 2. 12; 3. 12

Maximum toleration: 1. 26; 2. 26; 3. 27

2. Intensity discrimination

14 → 24

1V: 15, +, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 18, -, (✓);
22, =, (✓); 23, +, (X); 17, +, (✓); 18, -, (✓);
15, -, (✓); 18, -, (✓);

0.75V: 17, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 14, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓);
16, -, (X); 19, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 18, -, (✓);
19, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓);

0.50V: 21, -, (✓); 14, +, (✓); 14, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 14, +, (✓); 23, -, (X);
19, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

0.25V: 20, -, (X); 22, -, (X); 22, +, (X); 19, -, (✓);
14, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 21, -, (X); 17, -, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 21, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | |
|---------------|--------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>10</u> | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 2 Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>23</u> | Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 3 Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>29</u> | Voltage <u>25</u> |
| 5 Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>113</u> | Voltage <u>24</u> |
| 4 Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>55</u> | Voltage <u>24.5</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

2, (✓); 4, (✓); 4, (✓); 1, (✓);
5, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓); 3, (✓);
5, (✓); 2, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

4, (X → 5); 3, (✓); 6, (✓); 2, (✓);
1, (✓); 2, (X → 1); 6, (✓); 4, (✓);
1, (✓); 6, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
 1 2 3 4 5 6

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

| | | | |
|-------------------|---------------|-------------------|-----------------|
| <u>F</u> (✓); | <u>X</u> (✓); | <u>3</u> (x → 8); | <u>W</u> (✓); |
| <u>L</u> (✓); | <u>Z</u> (✓); | <u>9</u> (✓); | <u>R</u> (✓); |
| <u>8</u> (✓); | <u>H</u> (✓); | <u>9</u> (✓); | <u>P</u> (✓); |
| <u>6</u> (x → 7); | <u>E</u> (✓); | <u>V</u> (✓); | <u>I</u> (x →); |
| <u>7</u> (✓); | <u>I</u> (✓); | <u>J</u> (✓); | <u>I</u> (✓); |

王源祥

Questionnaire

Name: 杨文强

Gender: 男

Age: 24

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 12; 2. 13; 3. 13
 Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 28; 3. 28

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 15, f, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 18, -, (✓); 18, f, (✓);
21, f, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
24, -, (✓); 16, f, (✓);

0.75V: 20, f, (✓); 20, f, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 22, f, (✓);
21, f, (✓); 20, f, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
17, f, (✓); 24, f, (✓);

0.50V: 24, f, (✓); 16, f, (✓); 15, f, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
15, f, (✓); 24, f, (✓); 18, f, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
20, f, (✓); 20, -, (✓);

0.25V: 15, f, (✓); 19, f, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
24, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 24, f, (✓);
15, f, (✓); 23, -, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | |
|---------------|-------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>12</u> | Voltage <u>28</u> |
| 2 Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>20</u> | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 3 Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>33</u> | Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 5 Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>48</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 4 Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>45</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

1, (✓); 3, (✓); 1, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓);
5, (✓); 3, (✓); 5, (✓); 2, (✓); 4, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
 (2 3 4 5 6

5. Super-resolution distinguish

6 (✓); 4 (✓); 2 (✓); 4 (✓); 5 (✓);
6 (✓); 3 (✓); 1 (✓); 2 (✓); 1 (✓)

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

1 (✓); Q (x) ^{→ 0}; T (✓); L (✓); 8 (✓);
R (✓); 5 (✓); K (✓); J (✓); 0 (✓);
4 (✓); 3 (x) ^{→ 8}; W (✓); F (✓); S (x) ^{→ 8};
E (✓); D (✓); C (x) ^{→ 0}; G (✓); 6 (✓)

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[Faint, illegible handwritten notes and scribbles covering the lower half of the page.]

12

Questionnaire

Name: 李

Gender: 男

Age: 23

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 12

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 28

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 18, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
24, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓);

0.75V: 24, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓);
0.75V: 18, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓);
21, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
15, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

0.50V: 23, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓);
15, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
23, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓);

0.25V: 20, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓);
19, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

- | | | |
|---------------|-------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>12</u> | Voltage <u>28</u> |
| 2 Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>25</u> | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 3 Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>33</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 5 Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>40</u> | Voltage <u>25.5</u> |
| 4 Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>50</u> | Voltage <u>26</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

4, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);
2, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓);
5, (✓); 1, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

4, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (×); 2, (×);
6, (✓); 1, (✓); 5, (✓); 5, (✓);
3, (✓); 6, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
1 2 3 4 5 6

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

6 (✓); R (✓); E (✓); O (✓);
z (✓); H (✓); 3 (✓); C (X)O;
T (✓); 1 (X)7); X (✓); G (✓);
D (X)0); v (✓); A (✓); 8 (✓);
9 (✓); B (✓); K (✓); P (✓);

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Questionnaire

Name: 肖凡雨

Gender: 男

Age: 25

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 28

15-25

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 21, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓);

16, +, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓);

18, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

0.75V: 23, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 20, -, (X);

17, -, (✓); 23, -, (X); 23, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓);

17, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓);

0.50V: 20, -, (✓); 19, -, (X); 22, +, (✓); 16, +, (✓);

18, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 24, -, (X);

15, +, (✓); 18, -, (X);

0.25V: 22, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 17, -, (X);

19, +, (X); 17, -, (✓); 15, -, (X); 19, +, (X);

15, -, (X); 19, +, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 10

Voltage 28

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 22

Voltage 27.5

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 34

Voltage 27

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 105

Voltage 26

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 45

Voltage 26.5

4. Texture discrimination

3, (✓); 5, (✓); 4, (✓); 3, (✓);

2, (✓); 2, (✓); 4, (✓); 5, (✓);

1, (✓); 3, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

6, (✓); 3, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓);

1, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);

3, (✓); 1, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
1 2 3 4 5 6

13

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

X (✓); H (✓); V (✓); C (✓);
V (✓); Z (✓); I (✗); O (✗);
P (✓); 4 (✓); J (✓); T (✓);
I (✓); K (✓); E (✓); A (✓);
R (✓); 3 (✓); G (✓); 9 (✓);

背A面

10

Questionnaire

Name: 李响

Gender: 男

Age: 24

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 27; 3. 28

15-25

2. Intensity discriminatio

1V: 21, +, (✓); 24, -, (X); 22, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

22, +, (✓); 16, -, (X); 15, +, (✓); 19, -, (X);

22, +, (✓); 21, -, (X);

0.75V: 16, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 16, -, (X); 20, -, (X);

16, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓);

22, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

0.50V: 23, +, (✓); 17, -, (X); 24, -, (X); 16, +, (✓);

21, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 20, -, (X); 19, -, (X);

23, -, (X); 20, -, (X);

0.25V: 22, +, (✓); 18, -, (X); 19, -, (X); 22, +, (X);

20, +, (X); 23, +, (✓); 15, +, (X); 16, +, (✓);

18, +, (✓); 15, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

1 Rough rock: Vibration frequency 10 Voltage 27

2 Sandpaper: Vibration frequency 22 Voltage 26.5

3 Denim: Vibration frequency 33 Voltage 26

5 Glass: Vibration frequency 102 Voltage 25

4 Silk: Vibration frequency 48 Voltage 25.5

4. Texture discrimination

3, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (✓); 4, (✓);

2, (✓); 5, (✓); 1, (✓); 3, (✓);

5, (✓); 1, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

1, (✓); 2, (X>1); 4, (✓); 3, (✓);

2, (✓); 4, (✓); 5, (✓); 5, (✓);

6, (✓); 1, (✓);

1) > 0 0 0
1 2 3 4 5 6

14

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

8, (X); E, (✓); F, (✓); 2, (✓);
Y, (✓); T, (✓); 3, (✓); M, (✓);
V, (✓); N, (✓); 4, (✓); G, (✓);
A, (✓); R, (✓); 0, (✓); J, (X);
L, (✓); Q, (✓); 7, (✓); Z, (✓);

李銘

15

Questionnaire

Name: 宇佐

Gender: 男

Age: 28

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 12; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 29

15-25

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 24, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
23, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓);
24, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓);

0.75V: 21, -, (✓); 21, -, (✗); 19, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓);
19, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓);

0.50V: 23, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 17, -, (✗);
16, -, (✓); 15, -, (✗); 23, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
18, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓);

0.25V: 21, +, (✓); 20, -, (✗); 23, -, (✗); 19, +, (✓);
15, -, (✗); 16, -, (✗); 16, +, (✗); 24, +, (✗);
24, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | | |
|---|-------------|--------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 | Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>12</u> | Voltage <u>28</u> |
| 2 | Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>20</u> | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 3 | Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>35</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 5 | Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>110</u> | Voltage <u>24</u> |
| 4 | Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>60</u> | Voltage <u>25</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

5, (✓); 4, (✓); 2, (✓); 1, (✓);
4, (✓); 2, (✓); 5, (✓); 2, (✓);
3, (✓); 1, (✓);

5. Super-resolution distinguish

2, (✓); 4, (✓); 6, (✓); 5, (✗→4);
1, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓);
2, (✓); 1, (✓);

1 > 0 0 0
1 2 3 4 5 6

15

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

G (x→S); 5 (✓); 9 (✓); T (✓);
8 (✓); A (✓); B (x→3); S (✓);
0 (✓); K (✓); L (✓); F (✓);
2 (✓); E (✓); J (✓); C (✓);
Y (✓); H (✓); I (✓); V (✓);

39e

Questionnaire

Name: 彭国祥

Gender: 男

Age: 24

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 12; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

15 → 5

1V: 17, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
21, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓);

0.75V: 18, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 20, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
15, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

0.50V: 24, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓);
21, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓);

0.25V: 21, +, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓);
15, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 16, +, (✓);
23, +, (✓); 21, +, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | | |
|---|-------------|-------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 | Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>8</u> | , Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 2 | Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>22</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 3 | Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>34</u> | Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 5 | Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>97</u> | Voltage <u>24.5</u> |
| 4 | Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>45</u> | Voltage <u>25.5</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

1, (✓); 2, (✓); 3, (✓); 5, (✓); 2, (✓);
4, (✓); 1, (✓); 5, (✓); 2, (✓); 5, (✓);

16

1) > 000
1 2 3 4 5 6

5. Super-resolution distinguish

~~4~~, (N); ~~3~~, (N); ~~6~~, (N); ~~2~~, (N); ~~3~~, (N);
~~4~~, (N); ~~4~~, (N); ~~6~~, (N); ~~3~~, (N); ~~1~~, (N);

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

~~R~~, (N); ~~I~~, (N); ~~Y~~, (N); ~~C~~, (N); ~~L~~, (N);
~~V~~, (N); ~~U~~, (N); ~~G~~, (N); ~~X~~, (N); ~~Q~~, (N);
~~M~~, (N); ~~1~~, (N); ~~K~~, (N); ~~9~~, (N); ~~B~~, (N);
~~F~~, (N); ~~Z~~, (N); ~~4~~, (N); ~~H~~, (N); ~~6~~, (N);

彭國祥

17

Questionnaire

Name: 杨帆

Gender: 男

Age: 25

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 12; 2. 12; 3. 12
 Maximum toleration: 1. 28; 2. 28; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 24, +, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓)
18, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓)
21, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓)

0.75V: 23, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓)
20, +, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓)
23, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓)

0.50V: 22, -, (✓); 15, -, (✓); 15, +, (✓); 19, +, (✓)
20, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓)
15, -, (✓); 22, -, (✓)

0.25V: 18, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 18, -, (✓)
22, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓)
16, -, (✓); 19, +, (✓)

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | | | | | |
|---|-------------|---------------------|------------|---|---------|-------------|
| 1 | Rough rock: | Vibration frequency | <u>11</u> | , | Voltage | <u>28</u> |
| 2 | Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency | <u>20</u> | | Voltage | <u>27.5</u> |
| 3 | Denim: | Vibration frequency | <u>34</u> | | Voltage | <u>27</u> |
| 5 | Glass: | Vibration frequency | <u>115</u> | | Voltage | <u>25</u> |
| 4 | Silk: | Vibration frequency | <u>58</u> | | Voltage | <u>26</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

4, (✓); 1, (✓); 1, (✓); 3, (✓); 1, (✓)
5, (✓); 1, (✓); 2, (✓); 2, (✓); 3, (✓)

17 | 1) > 0 0 0
 1 2 3 4 5 6

5. Super-resolution distinguish

5 (✓) 6 (✓) 1 (✓) 1 (X) 6 (✓)
 3 (✓) 2 (✓) 3 (✓) 5 (✓) 5 (X) 4

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

Q (X) 0 S (✓) Y (✓) 1 (✓) 9 (✓)
 4 (✓) N (✓) D (✓) 2 (✓) I (X) 1
 M (✓) F (✓) R (✓) A (✓) 7 (✓)
 T (✓) C (✓) 2 (✓) P (✓) 0 (✓)

[Handwritten signature]

18

Questionnaire

Name: 叶地一

Gender: 男

Age: 23

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 28

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 22, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓);
19, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓);

0.75V: 22, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 20, -, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
20, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓);

0.50V: 18, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
16, +, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

0.25V: 23, -, (✓); 18, -, (X); 20, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);
20, -, (X); 20, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
15, +, (✓); 16, -, (X);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | |
|---------------|--------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>7</u> | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 2 Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>16</u> | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 3 Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>30</u> | Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 5 Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>100</u> | Voltage <u>24</u> |
| 4 Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>50</u> | Voltage <u>25</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

2, (✓); 4, (✓); 5, (✓); 1, (✓); 5, (✓);
4, (✓); 4, (✓); 3, (✓); 5, (✓); 4, (✓);

18

1) > 000

12 3 4 5 6

5. Super-resolution distinguish

~~5, (✓); 2, (x); 5, (✓); 6, (✓); 3, (x);~~
~~3, (✓); 4, (✓); 1, (✓); 1, (x); 5, (✓)~~

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

~~R, (✓); U, (x); V, (✓); P, (✓); 7, (✓);~~
~~W, (✓); F, (✓); B, (✓); S, (x); 8, (✓);~~
~~A, (✓); 1, (✓); K, (✓); O, (✓); 5, (✓);~~
~~2, (✓); 3, (✓); D, (✓); H, (✓); 6, (✓)~~

叶地一

Questionnaire

Name: 洪颖

Gender: 男

Age: 27

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 14; 2. 13; 3. 14

Maximum toleration: 1. 29; 2. 29; 3. 29

16-26

2. Intensity discrimination

1V: 19, -, (✓); 16, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 22, +, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 22, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓);
16, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓);

0.75V: 17, -, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 20, -, (✓); 25, +, (✓);
16, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 18, +, (✓); 19, -, (✓);
22, +, (✓); 18, +, (✓);

0.50V: 22, -, (✓); 19, -, (✓); 17, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
21, -, (✓); 16, -, (✓); 25, -, (✓); 20, +, (✓);
17, -, (✓); 17, -, (✓);

0.25V: 25, +, (✓); 23, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓); 25, +, (✓);
20, +, (✓); 23, +, (✓); 24, +, (✓); 24, -, (✓);
20, -, (✓); 21, -, (✓);

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | |
|---------------|--------------------------------|---------------------|
| 1 Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>10</u> | , Voltage <u>28</u> |
| 2 Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>25</u> | , Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 3 Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>38</u> | , Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 5 Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>112</u> | , Voltage <u>24</u> |
| 4 Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>56</u> | , Voltage <u>25</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

2, (✓); 1, (✓); 3, (✓); 3, (✓); 2, (✓);
3, (✓); 5, (✓); 3, (✓); 4, (✓); 5, (✓);

19
 1) > 0 0 0
 (2 3 4 5 6

5. Super-resolution distinguish

~~6~~, (✓); ~~1~~, (✓); ~~3~~, (✓); ~~5~~, (✓); ~~1~~, (✓); ~~2~~
~~4~~, (✓); ~~2~~, (✓); ~~6~~, (✓); ~~3~~, (✓); ~~1~~, (✓); ~~2~~

6. Letters and numbers discrimination

~~6~~, (✓); ~~J~~, (✓); ~~E~~, (✓); ~~W~~, (✓); ~~V~~, (✓);
~~2~~, (✓); ~~X~~, (✓); ~~4~~, (✓); ~~Q~~, (✓); ~~S~~, (✓);
~~B~~, (✓); ~~Y~~, (✓); ~~Z~~, (✓); ~~T~~, (✓); ~~C~~, (✓);
~~R~~, (✓); ~~A~~, (✓); ~~D~~, (✓); ~~M~~, (✓); ~~F~~, (✓);

洪毅

20

Questionnaire

Name: 潘其其

Gender: 男

Age: 27

1. Intensity test

Detection threshold: 1. 13; 2. 13; 3. 13

Maximum toleration: 1. 27; 2. 28; 3. 29

2. Intensity discrimination

15-25

1V: 16, -, (N); 17, -, (N); 19, +, (U); 20, +, (U)
18, +, (M); 16, -, (N); 17, -, (U); 18, f, (U)
24, f, (M); 19, -, (U)

0.75V: 16, f, (M); 24, f, (U); 15, -, (U); 20, f, (M)
17, -, (U); 20, -, (U); 17, f, (U); 18, f, (U)
24, f, (M); 24, f, (M)

0.50V: 22, -, (U); 15, f, (M); 16, f, (M); 17, -, (U)
15, -, (U); 16, f, (M); 18, f, (U); 24, f, (M)
23, f, (M); 16, f, (U)

0.25V: 18, f, (U); 24, -, (M); 21, -, (U); 19, -, (U)
18, f, (U); 17, -, (U); 15, f, (U); 18, f, (U)
20, -, (U); 18, -, (M)

Note: (Reference voltage), (Test voltage), (Judgement)

3. Roughness perception

| | | | | |
|---|-------------|--------------------------------|---|---------------------|
| 1 | Rough rock: | Vibration frequency <u>10</u> | , | Voltage <u>27</u> |
| 2 | Sandpaper: | Vibration frequency <u>20</u> | | Voltage <u>26.5</u> |
| 3 | Denim: | Vibration frequency <u>35</u> | | Voltage <u>26</u> |
| 5 | Glass: | Vibration frequency <u>120</u> | | Voltage <u>25</u> |
| 4 | Silk: | Vibration frequency <u>60</u> | | Voltage <u>25.5</u> |

4. Texture discrimination

2, (M); 1, (M); 4, (M); 2, (U); 3, (U)
2, (U); 3, (U); 5, (U); 1, (U); 3, (U)

